

YOGA FOR WOMEN'S HEALTH: A CONTEMPORARY STUDY

*Atin Kumar Maity, State Aided College Teacher, Category II,
Department of Sociology, Swarnamoyee Jogendranath Mahavidyalaya,
Amdabad, Nandigram, Purba Medinipur, West Bengal, Pin-721650
E-mail ID atinmaity1994@gmail.com*

Abstract

Yoga is a Sanskrit word that refers to the union of mind and body that has been used in Eastern societies since 5000 years ago and has received a lot of attention from Western countries in recent years. It refers to physical, spiritual and mental practices that connect the body, mind and spirit. Yoga is said to enrich awareness while creating a mind-body-spirit balance. Today is the era of women and with women being versatile. It requires a lot of grace and finesse. Today's woman plays much more roles than her traditional housewife role. In the contemporary world, women play an equal role in the decisions of socio-economic and political life. However, with a fast-paced lifestyle and highly stressful environment, women suffer from various health problems, both physical and mental. From gynaecological diseases and stress, physical fatigue and beauty issues, pregnancy and depression, women around the world are dealing with a number of health related issues and in addition to wearing appropriate clothing and being a devotee of yogini meditation, asana and pranayama in yoga practice, yogi is highlighted for their harmonious attitude. This paper will focus on the health benefits of exercise in women's lives through the practice of yoga. It will also explore how yoga can significantly improve the quality of life for women in contemporary time studies.

Key words : Yoga, women, pregnancy, and health benefits.

Introduction

“Yoga is the journey of the self, through the self, to the self”. -The Bhagavad Gita.

The word ‘Yoga’ or ‘Yog’ is derived from ‘Yuj’, a Sanskrit word which means ‘to join’ or ‘to unite’. It is a practice that helps one connect with the inner mind or consciousness. It brings a connection between the body and the soul, thereby bringing perfect harmony within. Regular Yoga practice brings physical fitness, breath awareness, connection with the mind and finally the inner self. Modern yoga as exercise has often been taught by women to classes consisting mainly of women. This continued a tradition of gendered physical activity dating back to the early 20th century, in today’s age; women have become more conscious about their health. Along with participating in various sports, they are also going to the health club to keep themselves healthy. But not everyone gets the time or opportunity to exercise outside the home. So they can do yoga at home in less time to maintain health. Along with physical exercise, the beauty routine also becomes much easier through the practice of yoga. Yoga is very effective in beautifying yourself with a healthy body. You cannot make yourself beautiful with a weak body or broken health. Therefore, physical education and physical education must be done together. A healthy body will enhance the physical beauty. The role of women in every family is very important in modern society. It is very important for them to be healthy to play this role.

Especially women stay at home most of the time. Although hands and feet are exercised through housework, there is no special exercise of the internal organs of the body; that requires yoga. It will be possible to keep away excess fat, heartburn, indigestion, back and waist pain, headache, weakness etc. through yoga practice.

To prevent various Gynaecological diseases such as thyroid, anemia etc., girls need to practice yoga from a young age, besides, according to the physical and mental structure of girls, yoga is the best means of physical exercise. Yoga is essential for women working outside the home to relieve mental stress and physical fatigue. Regular half hour yoga practice even in busy schedule can avoid many physical complications and difficulties in future. Another aspect of women is motherhood. Regular yoga practice

reduces the chances of complications during pregnancy and delivery. I have only tried to highlight women's asana and pranayam.

History

- **Indra Devi:** - Indra Devi, was a pioneering teacher of yoga as exercise, and an early disciple of the 'father of modern yoga'¹ her popularization of yoga in America through her many celebrity pupils in Hollywood, and her books advocating yoga for stress relief, earned her the nickname 'first lady of yoga'. Her biographer, Michelle Goldberg, wrote that Devi 'planted the seeds for the yoga boom of the 1990s'. Modern asana-based yoga, Indra Devi (born Eugenie V. Peterson), the Russian pupil of the founder of yoga as exercise, Krishnamacharya, argued that yoga was suitable for well-to-do Indian women: "Yogic exercises since they are non-violent and non-fatiguing are particularly suited to a woman and make her more beautiful." The historian of modern yoga Elliott Goldberg notes that the normally progressive Devi was effectively arguing for "a gentle yoga for the fairer sex", deprecating the more energetic exercises such as Surya Namaskar. 1939 she opened the first yoga school in Shanghai, continuing to run it for seven years, mainly teaching American women.
- **Louise Morgan:** - The UK's leading teacher-training centers are known for their non-dogmatic approach to yoga. He is fascinated by the nervous system and its effects on the way we move and feel. His continued studies in the science of movement and breathing led him to a more embodied practice. Drawing on the deep knowledge and philosophy of yoga, Louise's classes are an exploration of sensation, movement and stillness. Louise has an inquiry-based teaching style, which enables students to better understand how their bodies move and feel so they can. Find their own stability, strength and 'ideal alignment' within an asana. In 1936, journalist Lewis Morgan interviewed the King of Aundha, Bhawanrao Srinivasrao Pant representative in the News Chronicle. His report proclaimed 'Surya Namaskar – The

¹ Mohan, A. G.; Mohan, Ganesh (5 April 2017) [2009].

Secret of Health', claiming that not only was the king and queen in perfect health, but the 60-year-old wife of the queen's tutor looked younger than her daughters.²

- **Marcia Moore:** - Marcia Moore was an American writer, astrologer and yoga teacher brought to national attention in 1965 through Jess Stearn's book *Yoga, Youth, and Reincarnation*. She was an advocate and researcher of the dissociative properties of the drug ketamine. Marcia Moore studied yoga in Calcutta in the 1950s, and trained as a yoga teacher under Swami Vishnudevananda in Canada in 1961; she opened the Sivananda Yoga Vedanta Centre in Boston in 1962.³ Her classes were, according to the journalist Jess Stearn, 'wholly attended by upper-middle-class fortyish housewives'.⁴ Stearn reflected on why their husbands did not join the classes; he supposed that the men were put off by how easily their wives performed the asanas, and being unfit office workers, felt they would lose face if seen to be less physical than their wives. Moore explained to Stearn that the women were more interested in caring for their bodies than their husbands, since they had been caring for that "package" all their lives, and they didn't want to "see the wrapping wrinkled and spoiled."⁵
- **India:-** Little is known of many of the women who helped to develop modern yoga in India, but one of Bishnu Charan Ghost's pupils in Calcutta was Labanya Palit, who published a manual of 40 asana, Shari ram Adam 'A Healthy Body', in 1955, a work admired by the poet and polymath Rabindranath Tagore.⁶

Gendered activity

The yoga scholar Mark Singleton notes that there has been a dichotomy between the physical activities of men and women since the start of European gymnastics. Men were "primarily concerned with strength and vigour while women were expected to cultivate physical attractiveness and graceful movement."⁷ This gendered approach continued as

² Goldberg, Elliott (2016), pp. 275- 276.

³ Goldberg 2016, p. 322.

⁴ Goldberg 2016, p. 323

⁵ "The women of Yoga". Ghost Yoga. Retrieved 16 December 2019.

⁶ Rao, Soumya (31 July 2019)

⁷ Singleton 2010, pp. 160–162.

the practice of yoga asana became popular in the mid-20th century. A masculinised form of yoga grew from Indian nationalism, favouring strength and manliness, and sometimes also a form of religious nationalism, and continues into the 21st century among Hindu nationalists like the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Singh. The yoga author and teacher Geeta Iyengar notes that women in the ancient Vedic period had equal rights to practice the meditational yoga of the time.⁸

Yoga Journal's survey in 1997 found that a little over 80 percent of readers were female; in 2003, the journal's advertising page reported 89 percent female readership.⁹ This is causing yoga to evolve as a female practice, taught by women to women.¹⁰

Leading “yoginis” women in modern yoga, include Nischala Joy Devi, Donna Farhi, Angela Farmer, Liliias Folan, Sharon Gannon, Sally Kempton, Gurmukh Kaur Khalsa, Judith Hanson Lasater, Swamini Mayatitananda, Sonia Nelson, Sarah Powers (founder of Insight Yoga), Shiva Rea, Patricia Sullivan, and Rama Jyoti Vernon.¹¹

In 1931 "Seal" posture in *Building the Body Beautiful*, the Bagot Stack Stretch-and-Swing System it closely resembles the modern yoga asana Salabhasana, locust pose.

⁸ Hodges 2007, pp. 65–66.

⁹ Strauss 2005, p. 78

¹⁰ Hodges 2007, p. 70

¹¹ Gates 2006,

Improve to Various Steps

With busy schedules & unhealthy eating habits, we have invited a lot of diseases and lifestyle issues. Today, every fourth woman is facing PCOS and infertility issues. Lack of physical activity in any form further adds to our problems. According to National Centre for Biotechnology Information about 23% of the urban Indian female population is obese. It is vital that one follows the below steps in order to improve overall health. This is required:-

- **Balance Diet** – Prefer a home-cooked meal over ready-to-eat or processed food.
- **Workout** – Exercise each day for at least 30 minutes. This could be a walk, gym, Sumba etc. It just needs to involve physical activity.
- **Yoga** – Many feel benefits of yoga for women is a myth, but that's not true. As per a recent study by National Centre for Biotechnology Information about 92.16% of people who practice yoga have found that yoga has changed their lifestyle for good.
- **Meditate** – Meditating helps reduce stress, relieves from anxiety and improves mental health
- **Water** – Water intake is crucial to keep body hydrated and clean from toxins. It even maximises brain function and prevents kidney stones.
- **Work-life balance** – Having a career is great, but one must ensure that they do have an active life as well. Spending time with family, going on a vacation not only act as a mood refresher but can improve our productivity as well.
- **Yoga** - A blessing from ancient time's yoga is a practice that has been around us for years. Recently, it has become a trendsetter not only in India but all over the world. The great thing about it is that you can do it from anywhere – home, ashram or your office. The basic premise is that it focuses on the inner self and self-awareness. There are three forms of yoga – pranayama (breathing exercises), asana (yoga postures) and savasana (rest periods).

It has been proven that regular yoga practice not only brings mental peace but also improves blood circulation, increases mindfulness, and improves metabolism and digestion thereby helping weight loss.¹²

Health and Beauty

Any respect would fall short of the place women hold in our hearts and society. But women are also stretched and stressed. While they look after everyone around them, who really looks after them? The answer lies in yoga - the balance that today's 'Beauty with Brains' requires!

“Above all, be the heroine of your life, not the victim.” — Nora Ephron.¹³

Yoga has been marketed to women as something that made them look younger, and that they could carry on learning or teaching into old age, a message taught by books such as Nancy Phelan and Michael Violin's 1963 *Yoga for Women*: “Most yoga teachers know ... of women who have astonished everyone ... discarding stiffness and tension for suppleness, slimness, serenity and poise”.¹⁴ The yoga models in the 1960s and 1970s wore “flattering and sexy fishnet stockings and a tight-fitting leotard top”.¹⁵

Your outer beauty is a reflection of your inner health. Yoga helps boost immunity by strengthening your immune system. Yoga says that many 'rivers' carry life in our bodies. Basically we do yoga to keep these rivers fresh. To regulate the flow of energy in these 72,000 rivers in our body, regular yoga exercises and pranayama are necessary. It helps us all to maintain overall health. You can also get glowing skin through asanas and pranayama. It balances the stress hormones in your body. When you are not stressed, your skin also glows.

¹² <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com>

¹³ <https://www.artofliving.org>

¹⁴ Newcomb 2007; Phelan & Violin 1979, p.16.

¹⁵ Newcomb 2007.

- **Cleanse Toxins:** By doing yoga asana and pranayama you can completely remove toxins from your body. Cleansing toxins is essential to maintaining your best health. Toxins that are not excreted from the body accumulate in your system, causing damage to the body's internal systems. Techniques like Kapalavati, Anulom Biloma help in removing harmful toxins from your system. Kapalbhathi is a type of pranayama that helps to cleanse the lungs and rid the skin of acne, rashes etc.
- **Hal asana:-**
 1. Lie on your back.
 2. Place your palms on the floor next to your body.
 3. Using abdominal muscles lift your leg up to 90 degrees.
 4. Press your palms firmly into the floor and push your feet behind your head.
 5. Lift your lower back slightly up the middle so that your toes touch the floor behind you.
 6. Try to bring your chest as close to your chin as possible. The palms of the hands will help hold the back like this. Hold the seat for a while.
- **Sarvangasana:-**
 1. Lie on your back.
 2. Slowly lift your feet off the floor and face the sky with your feet perpendicular to the floor & slowly lift your pelvis.
 3. Bring your entire body from your chest in front of your chin. Place your palms on your back to hold this seat.
 4. Try to keep your shoulders, torso, pelvis and legs in the same straight line.
 5. Try to touch your chin with your chest and keep your gaze on your feet.

Clothing and accessories

Yoga is a special way to lead a healthy and fit life. In the busy and complex modern life therefore yoga has become a part of daily life. A few seats on a 24-inch by 72-inch mat, with appropriate clothing, can change the color of your life. It has been found that people who practice yoga regularly have better mental strength, immunity and stress control than others. However, yoga is closely associated with exercise clothing. But this is no ordinary active wear; rather, there are special clothes for yoga, which will provide

comfort during exercise. Will establish emotional connection. There are four parts to yoga; such as sitting, standing, bending and twisting. This requires special clothing.

According to Fortune Business Insights, the global yoga apparel market was valued at US\$ 19.40 billion in 2020, which will reach approximately US\$ 40 billion by 2028. Along with this, the list of top label brands has increased Adidas, Allow-Yoga, Athlete Inc., Lulu lemon, Nike, Puma—even current craze Ralph Lauren and Tom Ford aren't left out to add yoga apparel to their collections. Women's yoga has created a large market for fashionable yoga clothing.¹⁶¹⁷

Inextricably linked with yoga is exercise clothing and accessories.

Inextricably linked with yoga is exercise clothing and accessories.

Pregnancy

Prenatal yoga is a type of yoga designed for pregnant women. Yoga is intended to create a balance between emotional, mental, physical, and spiritual dimensions. Prenatal yoga is about helping you prepare for childbirth by relaxing the body and focusing on safe techniques and poses in all stages of pregnancy.

Yoga can improve your physical and psychological health — and not just for the duration of your pregnancy. If you didn't practice yoga before pregnancy, it's best to talk to your doctor before starting any prenatal yoga classes.

¹⁶ Loffredi, Julie. 24 March 2019.

¹⁷ DiBlasio, Natalie (30 December 2014).

More benefits of doing prenatal yoga include:

- 1. Reduces stress and symptoms of depression and anxiety.** The combination of intentional movement and structured breathing can help alleviate symptoms of depression. Breathing in slow, rhythmic breaths activates the nervous system and blocks cortisol, which, in high amounts, has been linked to depression.
 - 2. Improves blood flow.** The stretching and movements in yoga help increase blood flow to your heart. Improved blood flow means more oxygen-rich blood is going to your baby. This keeps your baby on track for healthy development.
 - 3. Beters your labor experience.** Starting prenatal yoga in any trimester can help you better relax and stay positive once you go into labor. Meditation and breathing exercises have been shown to reduce pain and anxiety during labor. Being confident and building your coping abilities will also help you have a less painful labor experience.
 - 4. Helps you build a support system.** Prenatal yoga classes can also help your social life by connecting with other expectant moms. A strong support system makes childbirth and postpartum easier. Anxiety about the delivery process can make labor worse. Being able to talk through your experience and hear others' stories can be comforting.
- **Yoga During Each Trimester** The further along you are in your pregnancy, the less intense your workouts should be.
 - 1. The first trimester-** You may feel fatigued and sick during this trimester. Try to avoid overworking yourself. Doing yoga poses slowly and carefully will prevent you from feeling worse. Yoga can alleviate pregnancy symptoms like nausea and backaches.
 - 2. The second trimester-** At this stage, you'll want to avoid belly poses and sharp twists. If you've been practicing advanced poses like backbends and inversions — where your feet are above your head — you may want to modify them. Inversions can compress your lungs and cause severe discomfort.
 - 3. The third trimester-** During this time yoga should focus on restorative and hip opening postures. Gentle stretching will help reduce your aches and pains. Avoid lying on your back. Blocks and pillows can help you get into a comfortable, safe position.

4. **Safety Considerations** - Movement and exercise are great ways to stay healthy

during pregnancy, but pushing yourself too hard can be counterproductive.

5 Amazing Yogasanas during Pregnancy

1. Bhadrasana (Butterfly pose):

Buddha = Bound or Restrained, Kona = Angle, Asana = Pose or Posture.

This pose is pronounced as BAH-dash-cone-AHS-Ana.

The posture is named Badhakonasana because of the way it is carried out – both the feet tucked close to the groin, clasped tightly with the hands as though tied or bound together in a particular angle. It is also popularly known as the Butterfly Pose because of the movement of the legs during the posture, giving the appearance of a butterfly flapping its wings. The posture is also sometimes known as the Cobbler Pose.

Benefits:

It strengthens the pelvic region, improves flexibility in the groin and hip region, stretches the thighs and knees and reduces pain. Offers relief from menstrual discomfort and menopause symptoms. Helps in smooth delivery if practiced regularly until late pregnancy.

2. Trikonasana (Triangle Pose):

Trikona - Triangle; Asana - Pose

The asana is pronounced as Tree-kone-nah -sah-nah (Trikonasana).

Unlike most yoga postures, the Triangle Pose requires keeping the eyes open in order to maintain body balance.

Benefits:

It reduces back pain and stress, improves digestive function during pregnancy and enhances hip flexibility.

3. Marjariasana (Cat Pose/Cow Pose):

Marjari = Cat; *Asana* = Posture or Pose.

The practice of Cat Pose (Marjaryasana) The word marjariasana is formed by joining the Sanskrit words marjari, meaning cat, and asana, meaning posture¹⁸ Marjariasana involves sitting on all fours (two hands and two legs) and stretching the back like a cat while synchronizing the breath with the spinal movements¹⁹ and Cow pose when done together in one flow involves different muscles like lower back, middle back, upper back, core muscles, hips and pelvis. It is then important to strengthen joints such as the hips and knees.

¹⁸ Wisdom Library; The portal for Hinduism, Sanskrit, Buddhism, Jainism, Mesopotamia etc... 2021 cited 2022Nov5.

¹⁹ Saraswati S. Asana Pranayama Mudra Bandha. Cited 5 November 2022.

Benefit:

This is beneficial in the third trimester. It improves blood circulation, stretches the back and shoulders, making the spine flexible.

4. Parvatasana (Mountain Pose):

Parvatasana is a Sanskrit word in which 'Parvata' means mountain and asana means 'pose' or 'posture'. Hence, it is also called 'mountain pose' because the final position of the body resembles the shape of a mountain. Parvatasana is a part of Surya Namaskar asana. It is an ancient practice of offering prayers to the rising Sun early in the morning along with physical postures.²⁰

Benefit:

It improves lung capacity and makes costal and blood circulation is improved and body posture, relieves from back and neck pain and increases the flexibility of the hip.

5. Shavasana (Corpse Pose):

Shavasana is the pronunciation of the Sanskrit word 'savasana.' It's a resting and restorative pose, or asana, typically used at the end of a yoga session. The Sanskrit word actually means 'corpse pose', because students practicing this pose lay face-up on the ground, arms and legs comfortably spread, eyes closed.

²⁰ Hipparagi M, Gangadhar P. Suryanamaskar for human wellness. Internal of Physical Education, Sport and Hea. 2019; 6(4):81-4.

Benefit:

This yogasana cools the body, calms the mind and marks the end of the yoga session. Practice this after every asana to allow the body to relax in between the asanas.

- **Safety Measures:**

Yoga is highly beneficial for the entirety of nine months and pivotal for the mother and baby, it is strictly advised to get a medical opinion before starting pre-pregnancy yoga to understand which yogasana to practice during the particular stage of pregnancy. It is also advised to learn the correct postures of the asanas from a trained yoga instructor to avoid various problems and have a happy and safe pregnancy.

Yogini

Yogini is a female master practitioner of tantra and yoga, as well as a formal term of respect for female Hindu or Buddhist spiritual teachers in Indian subcontinent, Southeast Asia and Greater Tibet. The term is the feminine Sanskrit word of the masculine yogi, while the term 'yogin' IPA: is used in neutral, masculine or feminine sense. A yogini, in some contexts, is the sacred feminine force made incarnate, as an aspect of Parvati, and revered in the yogini temples of India as the Sixty-four Yoginis. Pioneering female teachers of modern yoga as exercise are sometimes described as yoginis, though the term principally denotes medieval tantric figures, whether goddesses or female practitioners, as recorded in tantric texts and the surviving yogini temples.²¹ In her 2006 book *Yogini*, Janice Gates describes the contributions of leading

²¹ Hatley Shaman (2007).pp. 12–21

'yoginis' Nischala Joy Devi, Donna Farhi, Angela Farmer, Liliias Folan, and Sharon Gannon.²²

Yogini refers to a female master of yoga. The male counterpart is called a yogi. In the literature of classical Sanskrit, the term also refers to 'enlightened goddess' and 'divine mother'. In addition to being devotees of meditation, asanas and pranayama, yoginis are recognized for their harmonious attitude and quality of grace.

Here are some quotes by great Yoginis.

"In an asana, the mind has to reach inside the body to find a quiet space until a point comes where perfect balance is felt". - Geeta Iyengar.

"Yoga is a way to freedom. By its constant practice, we can free ourselves from fear, anguish and loneliness".

"We must keep both our femininity and our strength."- Indra Devi.

"In today's world, both men and woman need motherhood, the nurturing motherly feeling, the feminine energy. By receiving this energy, it will make them independent and free." - Mata Amritanandamayi (Amma).

Conclusions

Women Yoga has an effective role in reducing stress, anxiety and depression which can be considered as complementary medicine. The reason behind the effect of yoga on given stress, anxiety and depression is not clear to us and it may be temporary and it is suggested that future studies are done to investigate the long term effect of yoga on stress, anxiety. Today, yoga is practiced around the world, bringing physical fitness and inner wellness to millions of women.

Irrespective of gender, religion, caste, caste, everyone should practice yoga asanas and pranayams daily through which we can keep our body healthy; besides keeping our

²² Gates 2006,

body healthy we can also impart knowledge to our future generations through which we can create a healthy and beautiful environment. It is our duty to develop and provide this healthy and beautiful environment.

“Yoga does not just change the way we see things, it transforms the person who sees”. - B.K.S. IYENGAR.

Bibliography

- Mohan, A. G.; Mohan, Ganesh (5 April 2017) [2009]. *“Memories of a Master”*. *Yoga Journal*.
- Goldberg, Elliott (2016). *The path of Modern Yoga: The History of an Embodies Spiritual Practice*. ISBN 978-1-62055-567-5. pp. 275-276
- Goldberg, Elliott (2016). *The path of Modern Yoga: The History of an Embodies Spiritual Practice*. Goldberg, Elliott (2016). Rochester, Vermont: Inner Traditions. ISBN 978-1-62055-567-5.
- Newcombe (2019). *Yoga in Britain: Stretching Spirituality and Educating yogis*. Bristol: Equinox Publishing. ISBN 978-1-78179-661-0.
- Rao, Soumya (31 July 2019). *“Filling a gap in history: Who were the Indian women who popularised yoga”*
- Singleton, Mark (2010). *Yoga Body: The Origins of Modern Posture Practice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. ISBN 978-0-19-539534-1.
- Hodges, Julie (2007). *“The Practice of Iyengar Yoga by Mid-Aged Women: An Ancient Tradition in a Modern Life”*.
- Mallinson, James; Singleton, Mark (2017). *Roots of Yoga*. Penguin Books. ISBN 978-0-241-25304-5.
- Strauss, Sarah (2005). *Positioning Yoga: balancing acts across cultures*. Oxford and New York: Berg. ISBN 978-1-85973-739-2.
- Hodges, Julie (2007). *“The Practice of Iyengar Yoga by Mid-Aged Women: An Ancient Tradition in a Modern Life”*.
- Gates, Janice (2006). *Yogini: Women Visionaries of the Yoga World*. San Rafael, California: Mandala Publications. ISBN 978-1-932771-88-6.

<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog/ritika-verma/yoga-for-womens-health-56568/>

<https://www.artofliving.org/in-en/yoga-for-women/yoga-women>

Newcombe, Suzanne (2007). *“Stretching for Health and Well-Being: Yoga and Women in Britain, 1960-1980”*.

Hatley, Shaman (2007). *The Brahmayamalatantra and Easy Saiva Cult of Yoginis*. University of Pennsylvania (PhD Thesis, UMI Number: 3292099). pp. 12–21

Gates 2006, pp. whole book (a chapter to each of these women).

Loffredi, Julie. “Stylish Athleticwear and Workout Clothes for women” *Forbes*. Retrieved 24 March 2019.

DiBlasio, Natalie (30 December 2014). “Retailers Rush to Tap Millennial ‘At leisure’ Market”. USA Today. McLean, Virginia.

Www.wisdomlib.org. Marjari [Internet]. Wisdom Library; The portal for Hinduism, Sanskrit, Buddhism, Jainism, Mesopotamia etc... 2021 [cited 2022Nov5]. Available from: <https://www.wisdomlib.org/definition/marjari#sanskrit>

Saraswati S. Asana Pranayama Mudra Bandha [Internet]. Ia804508.us.archive.org. 2022 [cited 5 November 2022]. Available from: https://ia804508.us.archive.org/31/items/aaa_20210704/aaa.pdf

Hipparagi M, Gangadhar P. Suryanamaskar for human wellness. *Internal of Physical Education, Spor and Hea*. 2019; 6(4):81–4. Available from: <https://www.kheljournal.com/archives/2019/vol6issue4/PartB/6-4-7-230.pdf>